

UNEXPECTED CONSEQUENCES OF PROVIDING ONLINE VIDEOS IN A SERVICE MATHEMATICS MODULE: WHAT ONE LECTURER NOTICED

Maria Meehan

School of Mathematics and Statistics, University College Dublin

This study describes how brief-but-vivid accounts of incidents kept over three consecutive offerings of a large, first year, service mathematics module, were analysed and three unexpected consequences of making online videos available to students were identified in the BBV accounts written during the third offering of the module. It was in this offering that students, for the first time, were given the option of attending lectures or watching online videos or both. The first unexpected consequence relates to how the lecturer struggled to view poor attendance at lectures differently; the second to a difference, observed by the lecturer, in the way that students engaged with tasks during lectures; and, the third, to how the lecturer realised that videos could be used to encourage students to take more responsibility for their learning. Though these changes could be described as subtle, they have not been reported in the literature relating to the provision of online lectures as an extra resource to university students. The study also provides an example of how the Discipline of Noticing can be used as a professional development tool for those implementing initiatives in their teaching.

INTRODUCTION

In MEI5, a paper describing how I introduced a selection of short online videos as a supplementary resource for students in a large, first-year, *Maths for Business* module in 2012/13 (Meehan, 2013) was presented. The paper describes how the introduction of these videos had been prompted, in part, by my reflections on a collection of brief-but-vivid accounts (Mason, 2002), that were written while teaching the module during the previous academic year, 2011/12. For the next offering in 2013/14, I made the entire content of the module available in the form of 67 short, online videos and gave students the option of attending lectures or viewing videos or both. During this third offering, I continued to write brief-but-vivid accounts. In total, over the three consecutive years of teaching the module, I had written 72 accounts. In this paper I describe how the accounts over the three years were analysed in order to address the following research question: What changes did I notice during the third offering of the module when students were given the option to attend lectures or watch videos or both?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online Videos and Live Lectures at the University Level

In the past decade technological advances have made it possible for lecturers to easily record lectures (live or otherwise) and provide them as an online resource for students. With the availability of online lectures at the university level, there has been a growing body of research examining their impact in a number of areas. Due to space restrictions, we highlight some of the main areas of research here along with some findings and provide a selection of references. For a more comprehensive review see for example, Meehan and McCallig (2019).

Students express satisfaction with the availability of online lectures and perceive them to be beneficial to their learning (Danielson, Preast, Bender, & Hassall, 2014; Traphagan, Kucsera, & Kishi, 2010). In general, students tend to use online lectures to replace, review, and/or revise the live lecture (Danielson et al., 2014; Howard, Parnell, & Meehan, 2017; Leadbeater, Shuttleworth, Couperthwaite, & Nightingale, 2013). Most studies address the key question of how the provision of online lectures impacts student performance, although it has been noted that research to date yields inconclusive results (e.g. Danielson et al., 2014; Inglis, Papliana, Trenholm, & Ward, 2011; Owston, Lupshenyuk, & Wideman, 2011). The impact on lecture attendance of making videos available has also been examined with some studies finding that while attendances drops, performance remains unaffected (Owston et al., 2011; Traphagan et al., 2010; Yoon, Oates, & Sneddon, 2014). The frequency with which students view online lectures and/or their viewing patterns, has also been studied (Leadbeater et al., 2013; Owston et al., 2011). Finally, there are studies that examine students' preferences for lectures and/or videos, the reasons behind the preferences, and the impact of resource usage on performance (Bassili, 2006; Inglis et al., 2011; Howard et al., 2017; Meehan & McCallig, 2019).

Online Videos and Live Lectures in *Maths for Business*

The study reported in Meehan and McCallig (2019) is based on data collected on lecture attendance, videos accessed, and mathematical achievement, prior to, and at the end of, the module, for the cohort of students taking *Maths for Business* in 2013/14 – the same cohort as in Offering 3 of this paper. The authors found that when videos are embedded in a structured manner in the module, students who engage with the content fall into one of four main categories – those that: mainly attend lectures; mainly use videos; use both videos and lectures to cover the same content; or, use both videos and lectures but rarely to cover the same content. They also found that time spent using either or both resources has a significant impact on learning. Howard, Meehan and Parnell (2017) conducted a further study examining the 2015/16 *Maths for Business* cohorts' use of live lectures and/or videos, and their reasons for choosing one or both of the resources. Not surprisingly, they identified patterns of resource-usage similar to that in Meehan and McCallig (2019). The labelled as “Switchers” those students who used both resources but rarely to cover the same content. Interestingly some of these students attended lectures for the first few weeks and then switched to viewing videos for the remainder of the semester. In terms of achievement, those who primarily attend lectures (with or without viewing videos) achieved on average the highest marks. Reasons for students' choice of resource(s) are also presented in Howard et al. (2017).

The Discipline of Noticing

Practitioners develop habits or routines that enable them to deal efficiently with daily practice. However, once formed, one may not think about whether these habits continue to be effective, or if there is a better way to act. Mason (2011) suggests that: “the mark of professional development is that participants can imagine themselves in the future acting responsively and freshly rather than habitually” (p. 38). He proposes the Discipline of Noticing as one such professional development tool and describes it as “a collection of practices which together can enhance sensitivity to notice opportunities to act freshly in the future” (Mason, 2002, p. 59).

A key practice advocated by Mason (2002) is to record an incident for the purpose of analysing it at a later date by writing a “brief-but-vivid” (BBV) account of it. A BBV account is brief in the sense that it does not contain extraneous information that detracts from the main incident, and vivid in the sense that it contains enough detail that someone who may have been there could easily recognize the incident. In addition, it should be an “account-of” (p. 40) the incident as opposed to an “account-for” (p. 40) it.

To *account-for* something is to offer interpretation, explanation, value-judgement, justification, or criticism. To give an *account-of* is to describe or define something in terms that others who were present (or who might have been present) can recognize (p. 41).

The challenge of writing BBV accounts has been noted by both Mason, and by others who engaged in using the Discipline of Noticing as a professional development tool (see Breen, McCluskey, Meehan, O’Donovan, & O’Shea, 2014 and references within for studies of university mathematics educators reflecting on practice).

Mason (2002) provides several suggestions for working with a collection of BBV accounts. One of these is “threading themes” (p. 119) which involves examining the set of accounts for similarities or common threads. By “labelling” a theme or practice, it may be easier to notice and recognize it in the future, and consequently respond freshly rather than habitually.

METHODOLOGY

This study relates to accounts kept during three offerings of *Maths for Business*. Offering 1 (O1) was in Semester 1 of 2011/12, while Offering (O2) and Offering 3 (O3) were in Semester 1 of 2012/13 and 2013/14 respectively. Students who had taken Ordinary Level Mathematics or who had achieved a D1 or less in Higher Level Mathematics in the Leaving Certificate Examination (or equivalent) were assigned to my class. The approximate number of students in my cohort for O1, O2, and O3 was 300, 200, and 170 respectively. In O1, the module was assessed by a midterm MCQ and a final examination. In O2 this changed to ten weekly quizzes, a midterm MCQ, and final examination, with the MCQ removed in O3.

Throughout O1 and O2 of *Maths for Business* I kept BBV accounts of incidents that occurred, usually during lectures. Although every effort was made to write accounts that were brief, vivid and provided an “account-of” an incident, occasionally I lapsed into “accounting-for”. Having kept BBV accounts for the duration of the first two offerings, I noticed themes developing and became sensitised to some issues. Consequently, during O3 I often felt the need to “account for” incidents when writing accounts and many of them might not strictly qualify as BBV accounts. However I included them in the analysis as the context, “actors” and nature of the incidents were clear and made them suitable for analysis in this research.

Table 1 gives the number of accounts written for each of the three offerings, and the number of lectures for which an account was written. Some accounts, while describing an incident or incidents during a lecture, were divided into smaller, self-contained sections which I call segments. These segments formed the units of analysis.

Table 2 describes the context of each segment. In *Maths for Business*, I used a combination of “traditional” lecturing (During Lecture) and Inclass Exercises (IE). The latter describes the

context where I asked students to work on tasks during lectures, by themselves or in small groups, while I walked around. Some segments relate to incidents before the lecture or immediately after the lecture, or to thoughts I had while writing the accounts.

Table 1: For each offering, the number of accounts written and associated segments, and the number of lectures about which accounts were written.

	Number of Accounts	Number of Segments	Number of Lectures
2011/12	22	48	19
2012/13	24	44	20
2013/14	26	38	26
Total	72	130	65

Table 2: The number of segments relating to each context

	Before Lecture	During Lecture	Inclass Exercise	After Lecture	Writing Accounts	Student Forum	Total
2011/12	6	18	9	8	5	2	48
2012/13	4	17	13	5	7	1	47
2013/14	1	17	19	1	5	0	43
Total	11	52	41	14	17	3	138

The segments were uploaded to Nvivo where each was coded for the context to which it referred, and also the “actors” involved: self; individual student; small group of students; and, entire class. Additionally, each segment was coded for its content. It was possible for a segment to be given multiple codes. Some codes were then arranged under a category. An as example, a category named “Student Progress” had as its codes: Monitoring Student Progress; Positive Student Progress; “I haven’t got a clue”; and, Lack of Student Progress. Using Nvivo it was possible to identify which codes were prevalent in each of the three offerings, and in this way, identify any changes in what was noticed over the three offerings.

RESULTS

In this section, three changes that I noticed during O3 are presented. While attendance at lectures was poor in the three offerings, the first change relates to my own reaction to low attendance – my frustration in O1 and O2, and how during O3, I had to remind myself to react differently to it. The second change noted was a difference in students’ on-task behaviour during IEs in O3 when compared with O1 and O2. The third change relates to how the availability of the videos during O3 helped me address the challenge of students who struggled to become independent mathematical learners in the transition to university.

Reacting to Low Attendance in Lectures

While attendance at lectures during O1 and O2 was not recorded, there are eight and seven segments respectively from the accounts of each offering where attendance is noted. As each

semester proceeded, it is usually poor attendance that was noted. For example: “I approximate that I had less than one third of the class attending last week. [...] There are approximately 80 students out of 300 when I start the lecture” (L22, W8, O1). Similar examples occurred during O2. The morning after Halloween: “I count 38 [out of 200] present when I start the lecture a few minutes after 10am, although some more enter in ones and twos after that” (L23, W8). One lecture time seemed more popular than others: “The 2pm lecture on a Monday always has a bigger crowd than the two 10am lectures” (L19, W7, O1).

Some consequences of students missing lectures were noted. For example, lack of progress by some on an IE could be explained by previous absences:

It is a business example, identical to one I did last Tuesday but with the numbers changed. I walk up the right hand side of the theatre. One student has a blank page. He tells me he doesn't know what to do. I ask him if he was at last Tuesday's lecture and he says no. I throw my hands up and say “Engagement” and walk away. A similar interaction occurs with two other students (L24, W9, O1).

From this account and some of the actions I take in response to poor attendance noted in other accounts, it is apparent that poor attendance frustrated me. In W9, O1 and W5, O2 I sent an email to the class voicing my concerns over poor attendance and engagement. In L25, W9, O1, on noticing that “I have a much bigger crowd than usual for a Tuesday morning lecture”, I (pointlessly?) proceeded to lecture those present on the importance of attending lectures. In L15, W5, O2, on finding 30 students present when I arrived at the lecture just before 10am, “I decide to take attendance and pass three make-shift attendance sheets around the theatre”. When the lecture ended, 94 students were present.

The availability of the videos meant that even if attendance at lectures remained poor, what had to change was my reaction to it. The first indicator that the videos might have implications for how I react actually occurred during O2 when the supplementary videos were available. On the morning after Halloween described above, I introduced the technique of Gaussian Elimination. I asked the class to try one:

As there are now approximately 60 people present I get to look at what most people are doing. Most are making progress and getting through the problem in the systematic way I suggested. What about the 140 who weren't here today? I am glad I have my videos.

Otherwise I really think I'd have to go over it all again in detail on Monday (L23, W8).

On accessing the daily views of a video example of Gaussian Elimination in the days before it was examined on the weekly quiz, I noted that there were 23, 19, 5, 20, 17 and 107 views (W11, O2). I realised that nonattendance at lectures did not necessarily imply that students were not engaged. And rather than feel obliged to (perhaps begrudgingly) help those who missed a lecture on a critical topic to catch up, I felt relieved that I could proceed guilt-free.

However old habits die hard and I had to remind myself during O3 that nonattendance did not automatically equate to nonengagement. From L15, W6, I note: “There were 67 present today – the usual faces I see”. In writing the aims for the next lecture I thought about how I would make my point to class the importance of attending lectures: “I plan to go in today and ask

them to do a marginal analysis example. I just want to show the people who didn't attend yesterday what they missed". And then I caught myself: "Ah! But what about the videos?"

On-Task Behaviour During Inclass Exercises

As outlined above in the account from L24, W9, O1 some students, who were unable to make any progress during an IE, admitted to having missed a previous lecture. Whether it was because of poor attendance or some other factors, it was not unusual for accounts to note a lack of progress during IEs, even on exercises that should have been revision. In O2, I asked the class to construct a total cost function from some information given:

As this was revision, I told the class I'd give them a minute to write down the function. I went up the right hand side of the lecture theatre. I looked in about 20 notebooks and approximately 5 had it perfectly right. Some of the others just smiled at me and said "Sorry, totally lost" or "Sorry, no idea" (L16, W6, O2).

During O3, I noted a distinct difference in the atmosphere during IEs:

Everything I asked them to do, they just put their heads down and did it. I remember from previous years that as I would walk up one side of the theatre you would hear the noise level rise from the other side and if you looked over, people would be turned in their seats talking to those around them (L10, W4, O3).

This behaviour continued throughout the semester, and was noted again in L23, W9, O3. Of course this may have been a particularly diligent cohort of students, however in week 9 I did wonder if the industry displayed in lectures might be due to the availability of videos:

The other thing that I have noticed is that unlike previous years, when I am going around [during an IE] I rarely come across someone who says "I wasn't here the last day". I used to find that so frustrating. I want to do an exercise in class, I walk around, and there always seemed to be lots of people who couldn't even start because they hadn't been at a previous lecture. Maybe the videos have eliminated the "odd-timers" from the picture – the people who knew they should be coming and would show up the odd-time? Maybe the videos have salved their consciences! (L24, W9, O3).

Taking Responsibility for Learning in the Transition to University

In O1-O3, the students in my class had taken OL Mathematics or equivalent, and it was not unusual for some to experience anxiety about studying mathematics at university. This in turn could make some students reticent to even attempt problems. During the first week of an offering, one student told me that she was not working on a task because she was "no good at maths" while another stated that she did not know what to do because she had taken OL Mathematics. Since this was the first week, nonattendance at lectures could not have been a factor, in the same way that it *may* have been in the segment above, where students declared during an IE that they were "totally lost" or had "no idea". When writing the account of an IE task where students were asked to compute the gross national product of an economy at two time-intervals given the function that modelled it, I wondered if some students were accustomed to a post-primary environment where the teacher took responsibility for *making* them learn mathematics, which resulted in a type of learned helplessness:

“What do I substitute for?” “I don’t know what you want us to do?” “Do you want us to sub that in there?” “What is t ?” About two people had done it correctly. I know I am not supposed to “account for” but some don’t seem to be reading the questions or stopping to think before they attempt to work something out. Are behaviours they have learned before arriving here, preventing them from engaging appropriately? (L9, W3, O1)

When students say they are “totally lost” or “haven’t got a clue” or seem at a loss as to how to tackle a problem, I feel an onus to help. But “How do I fix this in a class of 300?” (L9, W3, O1). At the start of O3, the manager of the Maths Support Centre (MSC) informed me that a small number of students arrived at the centre before the first quiz claiming they were (mathematically) lost. I thought it a poor use of the MSC tutors’ time to explain a topic from scratch to individual students when the videos were already there.

I told him to instruct his tutors to respond to a student who comes in saying “I haven’t got a clue”, by suggesting they watch a relevant video there and then, rather than have the tutors give their own explanations from scratch (Segment 6.3, W2, O3).

I further suggested to students that they could use the videos to be more specific about where they were getting stuck, and in this way the tutors and I could help them more effectively:

I started the lecture with a little speech about how I didn’t want to hear the phrase “I haven’t got a clue about ...” from anyone in the class. [...] I said that there was no reason for anyone not to have a clue as the videos were there and if stuck, I wanted them to watch them and instead say: “I am stuck at this exact part” (L7, W3, O3).

In this way, students could not “get off the hook” by declaring themselves “totally lost”. They had to take the first steps - find and watch a relevant video and identify the point of confusion.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A weakness of this study is that it relates to what one lecturer noticed in one module. However, in writing and examining the BBV accounts, I observed some subtle consequences of making videos available that have not appeared in other research in this area. Indeed, using the methodologies of other studies, it is difficult to see how they might. For example, the study by Meehan and McCallig (2019) identifies a cohort of students who consistently attend lectures (with or without using videos as complements). This study, specifically the second change described above, complements their quantitative findings, by shedding light on the difference that having students who choose to consistently attend lectures has on the atmosphere in the lecture, particularly one in which students are expected to work on tasks.

Using videos to encourage students to take more responsibility for their mathematical learning in the transition to university, is also a technique that others could use in their modules. It seems counterintuitive that by giving students the extra resource of videos, one is encouraging them to take control of their learning. For weaker students in particular, videos have more explanatory power than notes for example and hence may be more effective in achieving this.

Finally, as has been argued before (Breen et al., 2014) this study also shows how the Discipline of Noticing can be used in professional development. By keeping and analysing BBV accounts, I identified areas of my practice that could be improved. I also realised that a

belief I have as a lecturer is that it is my duty to help all students learn even if they only attend sporadically, or struggle to engage. No wonder I was frustrated by poor attendance and overwhelmed by lack of progress during IE! The videos have provided me with another way to help these students, and in doing so, have made for a much more contented lecturer.

REFERENCES

- Bassili, J. N. (2006). Promotion and prevention orientations in the choice to attend lectures or watch them online. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 22, 444-455.
- Breen, S., McCluskey, A., Meehan, M., O'Donovan, J., & O'Shea, A. (2014). A year of engaging with the discipline of noticing: Five lecturers' reflections. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 19(3), 289-300.
- Danielson, J., Preast, V., Bender, H., & Hassall, L. (2014). Is the effectiveness of lecture capture related to teaching approach or content type? *Computers and Education*, 72, 121-131.
- Howard, E., Meehan, M., & Parnell, P. (2017). Live lectures or online videos: students' resource choices in a first-year university mathematics module. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 49(4), 530-553.
- Inglis, M., Papliana, S., Trenholm, J., & Ward, J. (2011). Individual differences in students' use of optional learning resources. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27, 490-502.
- Leadbeater, W., Shuttleworth, T., Couperthwaite, J., & Nightingale, K. P. (2013). Evaluating the use and impact of lecture recording in undergraduates: Evidence for distinct approaches by different groups of students. *Computers and Education*, 61, 185-192.
- Mason, J. (2002). *Researching your own practice: The discipline of noticing*. London: RoutledgeFalmer.
- Meehan, M. & McCallig, J. (2019). Effects on learning of time spent by university students attending lectures and/or watching videos. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 35(2), 283-293.
- Meehan, M. (2013). Video killed the radio star: Will the university lecturer be its next victim? In T. Dooley, S. NicMhuirí, M. O'Reilly & R. Ward (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Fifth Conference on Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 212-223). Dublin: MEI.
- Owston, R., Lupshenyuk, D., & Wideman, H. (2011). Lecture capture in large undergraduate classes: Student perceptions and academic performance. *Internet and Higher Education*, 14, 262-268.
- Yoon, C., Oates, G., & Sneddon, J. (2014). Undergraduate mathematics students' reasons for attending live lectures when recordings are available. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 45(2), 227-240.
- Traphagan, T., Kucsera, J. V., & Kishi, K. (2010). Impact of class lecture webcasting on attendance and learning. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 58(1), 19-37.